

Electronic Supplement

Huber B.A. Beyond size: sexual dimorphisms in pholcid spiders

Table S1. Male and female tibia 1 lengths in 495 species of Pholcidae, with sample sizes and sources. The table lists only those species where at least five males and five females were measured.

Species	Male tibia 1 length (mm)	N ♂	Female tibia 1 length (mm)	N ♀	Reference
<i>Aetana abadae</i>	10,20	6	8,10	13	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana gaya</i>	7,60	10	5,30	11	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana indah</i>	8,84	5	6,70	8	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana kinabalu</i>	8,30	7	6,40	15	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana kiukoki</i>	8,20	48	6,10	56	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana lambir</i>	7,40	19	6,20	26	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana libjo</i>	8,60	6	6,70	9	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana loboc</i>	7,10	7	5,30	17	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana manansalai</i>	8,30	5	6,30	13	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana mokwam</i>	11,70	8	9,90	15	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Aetana omayan</i>	10,40	8	8,20	16	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Aetana ondawamei</i>	9,10	5	8,30	6	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Aetana poring</i>	6,80	5	5,10	12	Huber et al 2015a
<i>Anansus debakkeri</i>	1,07	7	1,03	8	Huber 2007
<i>Anopsicus ana</i>	0,73	9	0,81	8	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Anopsicus chiriqui</i>	1,72	15	1,54	9	Huber 1998c
<i>Anopsicus tico</i>	1,90	20	1,95	20	Huber 1998c
<i>Apokayana kapit</i>	11,30	8	8,20	6	Huber & Leh Moi Ung 2016
<i>Apokayana tahai</i>	8,30	5	6,70	5	Huber 2011
<i>Arenita fazendinha</i>	0,59	15	0,47	22	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Arnapa arfak</i>	6,80	5	4,70	7	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Arnapa tinoor</i>	6,60	28	4,50	37	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Arnapa tolire</i>	5,70	5	4,10	9	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Artema atlanta</i>	15,40	19	13,20	20	Aharon et al 2017
<i>Artema bunkpurugu</i>	19,80	8	16,10	20	Huber & Kwapong 2013
<i>Artema dhofar</i>	15,10	5	13,60	10	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Artema doriae</i>	14,50	19	8,30	20	Aharon et al 2017
<i>Artema ghubrat</i>	15,70	8	12,40	8	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Artema nephilit</i>	14,40	14	12,50	26	Aharon et al 2017
<i>Artema transcaspica</i>	13,10	13	10,80	24	Aharon et al 2017
<i>Aucana kaala</i>	0,91	8	0,85	13	Huber 2000

<i>Aucana petorca</i>	1,17	8	1,08	15	Huber 2000
<i>Aucana platnicki</i>	1,09	9	1,05	10	Huber 2000
<i>Aymaria conica</i>	7,70	8	5,10	13	Huber 2000
<i>Belisana airai</i>	1,15	6	0,97	21	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana aliformis</i>	6,68	8	5,45	17	Tong & Li 2008
<i>Belisana badulla</i>	4,50	6	3,10	11	Huber 2019
<i>Belisana bohorok</i>	3,81	9	2,95	24	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana cas</i>	3,50	8	3,04	9	Yao et al 2018
<i>Belisana douqing</i>	5,85	5	3,73	5	Chen et al 2009
<i>Belisana fiji</i>	4,44	17	3,42	17	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana gedeh</i>	2,00	8	1,79	17	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana gowindahela</i>	3,70	32	3,10	44	Huber 2019
<i>Belisana hormigai</i>	4,90	16	3,70	12	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana inthanon</i>	4,64	5	3,55	6	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana junkoae</i>	4,42	8	3,51	6	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana kendari</i>	4,66	5	3,52	6	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana ketambe</i>	1,55	20	1,39	30	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana keyti</i>	3,93	6	3,20	12	Huber 2005a, 2019
<i>Belisana kinabalu</i>	3,97	11	3,33	8	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana leumas</i>	2,08	6	1,44	11	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana leuser</i>	4,79	20	3,54	20	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana nahtanoj</i>	3,48	8	2,89	12	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana nujiang</i>	2,99	5	2,61	6	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana ratnapura</i>	3,45	26	3,19	31	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana scharffi</i>	4,60	11	3,70	13	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana sepaku</i>	4,23	7	3,42	13	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana tambligan</i>	5,73	15	4,07	12	Huber 2005a
<i>Belisana yap</i>	3,58	5	2,50	5	Huber 2005a
<i>Blancoa piacoa</i>	2,21	8	1,28	16	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Boconita yacambu</i>	13,50	10	10,30	7	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Buitinga asax</i>	5,76	23	4,55	22	Huber 2003b
<i>Buitinga batwa</i>	4,70	9	3,75	5	Huber & Warui 2012
<i>Buitinga griswoldi</i>	3,27	11	2,92	21	Huber 2003b
<i>Buitinga kadogo</i>	2,31	6	1,96	14	Huber 2003b
<i>Buitinga mbomole</i>	5,94	29	4,89	15	Huber 2003b
<i>Buitinga mulanje</i>	3,58	8	3,02	13	Huber 2003b
<i>Buitinga ruwenzori</i>	5,19	8	4,26	17	Huber 2003b
<i>Buitinga safura</i>	5,65	39	4,75	50	Huber & Hopf 2004

<i>Buitinga uzungwa</i>	5,54	24	4,28	24	Huber 2003b
<i>Buitinga wataita</i>	6,40	35	5,20	25	Huber & Warui 2012
<i>Calapnita mae</i>	7,40	5	5,90	16	Huber 2017
<i>Calapnita nunezae</i>	7,60	23	6,20	29	Huber 2017
<i>Calapnita saluang</i>	6,90	41	6,06	51	Huber 2011, Huber 2017
<i>Canaima arima</i>	1,83	12	1,28	10	Huber 2000
<i>Canaima avila</i>	2,80	5	2,02	5	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Canaima guaquirá</i>	2,14	5	1,65	13	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Canaima loca</i>	3,00	7	2,40	7	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Cantikus erawan</i>	7,10	21	6,30	20	Huber et al 2016a
<i>Cantikus halabala</i>	8,00	12	7,00	6	Huber et al 2016a
<i>Cantikus khaolek</i>	11,70	5	9,30	5	Huber et al 2016a
<i>Cantikus namou</i>	10,10	5	8,00	8	Huber 2011
<i>Cantikus sudhami</i>	9,90	7	8,10	7	Huber et al 2016a
<i>Carapoia agilis</i>	2,90	9	2,30	19	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia alagoas</i>	6,80	7	5,20	17	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia brescoviti</i>	8,40	8	6,40	19	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia cambridgei</i>	12,40	33	9,40	22	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia capixaba</i>	7,60	7	5,60	15	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia carybei</i>	7,40	5	5,50	6	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia crasto</i>	9,50	10	6,50	9	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia dandarae</i>	8,70	15	6,40	15	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia divisa</i>	8,10	5	5,70	7	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia djavani</i>	2,40	8	1,90	17	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia fowleri</i>	11,70	41	7,30	19	Huber 2000
<i>Carapoia lutea</i>	9,80	92	6,90	70	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia macacu</i>	8,60	12	6,10	15	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia marceloi</i>	9,00	9	6,40	28	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia mirim</i>	6,80	9	5,10	11	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia munduruku</i>	11,30	39	8,20	24	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia nairae</i>	7,70	21	5,80	15	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia ocaina</i>	11,60	7	8,80	11	Huber 2000
<i>Carapoia pulchra</i>	8,70	14	5,90	24	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia rheimsae</i>	10,60	43	8,60	30	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia rubra</i>	14,70	12	11,90	9	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia septentrionalis</i>	6,50	10	4,90	11	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia suassunai</i>	7,70	27	5,50	29	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia tapajos</i>	4,84	5	3,80	10	Huber 2018

<i>Carapoia tenuis</i>	11,50	11	8,60	12	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia ubatuba</i>	8,90	7	6,70	15	Huber 2005c
<i>Carapoia una</i>	9,20	6	6,50	12	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia utinga</i>	7,30	5	4,90	6	Huber 2018
<i>Carapoia voltavelha</i>	9,10	5	6,30	9	Huber 2016b
<i>Carapoia zumbii</i>	8,30	7	6,30	7	Huber 2016b
<i>Chibchea amapa</i>	3,00	14	2,40	23	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Chibchea araona</i>	3,50	9	2,50	10	Huber 2000
<i>Chibchea hamadae</i>	4,30	7	3,20	9	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Chibchea ika</i>	3,90	9	2,70	10	Huber 2000
<i>Chibchea mapuche</i>	5,20	5	4,10	12	Huber 2000
<i>Chibchea picunche</i>	4,00	8	3,50	28	Huber 2000
<i>Chibchea salta</i>	3,80	19	3,30	5	Huber 2000
<i>Chibchea santosi</i>	2,56	5	2,10	23	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Chibchea silvae</i>	5,50	15	4,20	10	Huber 2000
<i>Chibchea tunebo</i>	3,90	5	2,90	5	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Chibchea uru</i>	0,76	5	0,68	6	Huber 2000
<i>Chisosa caquetio</i>	0,68	5	0,61	17	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Ciboneya antraia</i>	8,60	19	6,90	32	Huber & Pérez González 2001
<i>Coryssoenemis guacharo</i>	11,70	5	8,70	6	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Coryssoenemis simla</i>	9,70	10	5,90	10	Huber 2000
<i>Crossopriza lyoni</i>	13,97	26	12,95	36	Huber et al 1999
<i>Galapa baerti</i>	0,71	9	0,67	16	Huber 2000
<i>Hantu niah</i>	5,00	8	4,50	16	Huber 2016a
<i>Holocneminus huangdi</i>	2,19	14	2,19	31	Tong & Li 2009
<i>Hoplopholcus asiaeminoris</i>	13,70	23	10,80	10	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus bursa</i>	12,00	7	10,80	9	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus ceconii</i>	11,90	30	11,40	29	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus dim</i>	13,20	12	12,70	12	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus figulus</i>	8,94	5	8,40	13	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus forskali</i>	9,10	25	8,10	31	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus gazipasa</i>	9,58	8	9,20	7	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus labyrinthi</i>	11,30	120	10,70	213	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus longipes</i>	11,40	20	10,80	24	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus minotaurinus</i>	11,70	56	11,10	68	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus minous</i>	8,40	38	7,60	45	Huber 2020
<i>Hoplopholcus patrizii</i>	14,00	22	12,70	24	Huber 2020
<i>Ibotyporanga naideae</i>	2,01	7	2,00	12	Huber 2000

<i>Kelabita lambir</i>	10,50	9	8,00	20	Huber et al 2016a
<i>Khorata diaoluoshanensis</i>	5,59	7	5,12	14	Tong & Li 2008
<i>Khorata digitata</i>	7,42	6	6,85	5	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata dongkou</i>	4,45	10	4,04	14	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata epunctata</i>	7,43	6	7,01	13	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata flabelliformis</i>	5,44	5	5,07	18	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata luojinensis</i>	5,45	10	4,94	10	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata macilenta</i>	4,57	20	4,23	55	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata miaoshanensis</i>	5,18	13	4,47	34	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata paquini</i>	4,60	12	4,03	14	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata robertmurphyi</i>	4,06	5	3,86	25	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Khorata shao</i>	6,07	13	5,46	38	Yao & Li 2010
<i>Kintaqa buatong</i>	9,70	10	7,30	5	Huber et al 2016a
<i>Kintaqa schwendingeri</i>	8,00	19	6,00	10	Huber et al 2016a
<i>Leptopholcus borneensis</i>	7,34	5	6,80	14	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus budongo</i>	8,50	8	6,90	16	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus debakkeri</i>	8,40	9	7,10	15	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus gabonicus</i>	7,30	6	6,60	6	Huber et al 2014b
<i>Leptopholcus gracilis</i>	9,90	9	7,80	18	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus guineensis</i>	8,90	9	6,90	13	Huber 2009
<i>Leptopholcus gurnahi</i>	7,90	6	6,80	9	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus kandy</i>	7,60	6	7,10	10	Huber 2019
<i>Leptopholcus lokobe</i>	8,88	5	7,40	7	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus obo</i>	6,70	10	6,20	15	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus podophthalmus</i>	9,40	20	7,90	8	Huber 2019
<i>Leptopholcus talatakely</i>	7,60	35	6,60	34	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus tanikawai</i>	10,30	6	8,50	8	Huber 2011
<i>Leptopholcus tipula</i>	8,00	36	6,80	65	Huber 2009
<i>Litoporus curimagua</i>	8,30	15	4,30	7	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Litoporus iguassuensis</i>	7,30	30	3,80	52	Huber et al 2013
<i>Litoporus lopez</i>	7,80	18	3,90	6	Huber 2000
<i>Litoporus pakitza</i>	8,54	5	5,60	5	Huber 2000
<i>Magana velox</i>	0,50	6	0,52	9	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Mecolaesthus bienmesabe</i>	10,10	7	6,90	5	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus chicha</i>	6,20	6	4,70	7	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus cornutus</i>	5,70	17	4,10	19	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus fallax</i>	7,70	31	5,60	21	Huber & Villarreal 2020

<i>Mecolaesthus grandis</i>	9,50	9	6,30	9	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus lechosa</i>	11,30	8	7,50	6	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus limon</i>	8,40	6	5,40	5	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus longipes</i>	11,40	9	8,20	12	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus longissimus</i>	11,50	56	7,50	33	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus mucuy</i>	5,30	9	4,10	5	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus multidenticulatus</i>	8,90	10	6,20	9	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus niquitanus</i>	7,10	11	4,90	21	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus tabay</i>	5,00	5	3,60	6	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Mecolaesthus tuberculosus</i>	9,40	15	5,90	8	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Meraha krabi</i>	8,10	6	6,80	12	Huber et al 2016a
<i>Mesabolivar acrensis</i>	7,70	6	4,30	44	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar amadoi</i>	10,20	15	7,00	25	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar aurantiacus</i>	15,20	108	10,80	85	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar azureus</i>	9,90	12	7,40	22	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar baianus</i>	16,40	34	12,00	50	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar bico</i>	11,70	10	7,80	12	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar bicuspis</i>	17,00	5	12,90	13	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar brasiliensis</i>	11,30	32	8,70	30	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar buraquinho</i>	12,40	68	9,20	59	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar caipora</i>	11,90	16	8,80	7	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar catarinensis</i>	14,10	9	11,50	5	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar cavicelatus</i>	4,70	42	3,30	55	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar charrua</i>	12,40	14	9,80	11	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar claricae</i>	13,20	9	9,50	14	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar cyaneomaculatus</i>	15,60	9	12,20	11	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar cyaneotaeniatus</i>	14,20	45	10,90	41	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar difficilis</i>	4,70	6	3,70	8	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar eberhardi</i>	12,10	57	8,70	44	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar forceps</i>	4,11	11	2,68	11	Machado et al 2007
<i>Mesabolivar gabettae</i>	8,30	5	5,40	13	Huber 2015
<i>Mesabolivar goitaca</i>	8,58	5	5,40	13	Huber 2015
<i>Mesabolivar guapiara</i>	14,30	10	12,70	12	Paredes-Munguia & Teixeira 2019
<i>Mesabolivar huambisa</i>	11,80	6	8,30	5	Huber 2000
<i>Mesabolivar huanuco</i>	16,40	19	12,20	19	Huber 2000
<i>Mesabolivar iguazu</i>	10,50	65	7,60	50	Huber 2018

<i>Mesabolivar inmanis</i>	17,40	5	14,30	12	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar jamari</i>	9,80	5	5,80	7	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar kaingang</i>	14,40	12	12,40	9	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar kathrinae</i>	9,40	56	7,40	62	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar mairyara</i>	5,86	7	4,95	10	Machado et al 2007
<i>Mesabolivar maraba</i>	8,70	5	4,70	7	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar murici</i>	15,70	18	13,80	23	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar pau</i>	12,80	6	9,20	7	Huber 2015
<i>Mesabolivar rudilapsi</i>	10,20	5	6,60	5	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar sai</i>	15,90	20	12,70	18	Huber 2015
<i>Mesabolivar sepitus</i>	6,20	7	4,50	19	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar spinulosus</i>	12,20	31	9,60	30	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar tabatinga</i>	10,50	7	5,60	30	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar tamoio</i>	15,60	16	11,90	7	Huber 2015
<i>Mesabolivar togatus</i>	15,60	72	11,70	79	Huber 2018
<i>Mesabolivar unicornis</i>	3,20	7	2,10	5	Huber 2015
<i>Mesabolivar yucuma</i>	10,00	18	7,30	16	Huber 2018
<i>Metagonia argentinensis</i>	5,80	6	4,30	13	Huber 2000
<i>Metagonia asintal</i>	4,70	5	3,60	8	Huber 1998b
<i>Metagonia belize</i>	5,03	16	3,97	13	Huber 1998b
<i>Metagonia beni</i>	3,90	8	3,20	14	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Metagonia blanda</i>	5,53	15	4,84	12	Huber 1998b
<i>Metagonia conica</i>	6,70	120	4,70	100	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Metagonia delicata</i>	3,77	31	3,24	51	Huber 1997b
<i>Metagonia guttata</i>	4,40	7	3,60	12	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Metagonia latigo</i>	3,40	35	3,00	40	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Metagonia osa</i>	6,03	10	4,92	10	Huber 1998c
<i>Metagonia paranapiacaba</i>	2,19	12	2,00	16	Huber et al 2005
<i>Metagonia petropolis</i>	2,18	26	1,89	15	Huber et al 2005
<i>Metagonia reventazona</i>	5,50	11	4,28	16	Huber 1997b
<i>Metagonia rica</i>	7,14	65	5,43	38	Huber 1997b
<i>Metagonia talamanca</i>	4,55	6	3,82	15	Huber 1997b
<i>Metagonia uvita</i>	4,20	13	3,59	49	Huber 1997b
<i>Micromerys gracilis</i>	6,70	14	5,80	9	Huber 2001
<i>Micropholcus delicatulus</i>	6,90	8	5,70	16	Huber & Pérez González 1998
<i>Micropholcus evaluna</i>	5,80	9	4,80	6	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Micropholcus fauroti</i>	6,10	22	4,80	39	Huber 2011
<i>Micropholcus hispaniola</i>	7,20	36	5,40	56	Huber & Wunderlich 2006

<i>Micropholcus ubajara</i>	11,90	18	10,60	13	Huber et al 2014a
<i>Modisimus bribri</i>	7,92	79	5,20	71	Huber 1998a
<i>Modisimus cuadro</i>	6,10	9	4,30	12	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus culicinus</i>	2,10	5	1,53	5	Huber 1997a
<i>Modisimus david</i>	1,30	7	0,91	7	Huber 1997a
<i>Modisimus dominical</i>	9,16	14	6,85	25	Huber 1998a
<i>Modisimus enriquillo</i>	7,30	12	5,70	25	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus femoratus</i>	7,30	53	4,70	37	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus guatuso</i>	6,97	130	4,84	125	Huber 1998a
<i>Modisimus jima</i>	5,40	13	3,80	6	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus kiskeya</i>	7,30	39	4,60	40	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus makandal</i>	7,70	25	5,70	18	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus palvet</i>	5,56	5	4,10	6	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus paraiso</i>	6,30	5	4,10	8	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus repens</i>	3,90	7	2,60	6	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Modisimus seguin</i>	8,10	5	6,20	6	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus selvanegra</i>	6,30	17	3,90	12	Huber 1998a
<i>Modisimus simoni</i>	1,31	10	0,92	15	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Modisimus texanus</i>	6,80	10	4,50	15	Huber 1998a
<i>Modisimus toma</i>	4,40	13	2,80	12	Huber et al 2010
<i>Modisimus vittatus</i>	7,30	42	5,20	35	Huber et al 2010
<i>Muruta tambunan</i>	8,60	7	6,70	18	Huber et al 2016b
<i>Nerudia Arg38</i>	1,33	6	1,21	9	B.A. Huber unpubl. data
<i>Nerudia Arg58</i>	1,43	7	1,41	5	B.A. Huber unpubl. data
<i>Nerudia Mich20</i>	1,37	27	1,27	18	B.A. Huber unpubl. data
<i>Ninetis faro</i>	0,69	5	0,53	5	Huber et al 2014b
<i>Nipisa anai</i>	7,80	8	6,70	12	Huber 2017
<i>Nipisa bankirai</i>	7,60	11	6,00	9	Huber 2017
<i>Nipisa bidayuh</i>	7,90	5	6,40	5	Huber 2017
<i>Nipisa deelemanae</i>	7,40	6	6,30	11	Huber 2017
<i>Nipisa kubah</i>	9,90	13	8,40	11	Huber 2017
<i>Nipisa lehi</i>	9,20	12	7,50	14	Huber 2017
<i>Nipisa phyllicola</i>	7,92	61	6,62	51	Huber 2017
<i>Nipisa semengoh</i>	9,20	11	7,40	11	Huber 2017
<i>Nipisa subphyllicola</i>	9,20	31	6,90	50	Huber 2017
<i>Nyikoa limbe</i>	3,42	49	3,16	48	Huber 2007
<i>Paiwana pingtung</i>	10,40	15	8,50	11	Huber & Dimitrov 2014
<i>Panjange camiguin</i>	9,50	11	7,10	32	Huber & Nuneza 2015

<i>Paramicromerys betsileo</i>	5,34	20	4,06	27	Huber 2003a
<i>Paramicromerys coddingtoni</i>	3,88	10	3,03	14	Huber 2003a
<i>Paramicromerys marojeji</i>	5,03	11	3,51	18	Huber 2003a
<i>Pehrforsskalia conopyga</i>	5,40	7	4,50	16	Huber 2009
<i>Pholcophora americana</i>	1,64	11	1,47	13	Huber 2000
<i>Pholcus alloctospilus</i>	9,50	6	6,30	5	Zhang & Zhu 2009
<i>Pholcus alticeps</i>	10,40	21	9,50	28	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus ancoralis</i>	13,50	25	11,40	37	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus arayat</i>	11,90	15	10,30	12	Huber et al 2016c
<i>Pholcus arkit</i>	7,60	5	7,30	11	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus attuleh</i>	10,00	24	7,40	40	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus baguio</i>	12,30	19	10,70	16	Huber et al 2016c
<i>Pholcus bailongensis</i>	11,97	17	9,57	19	Yao & Li 2012
<i>Pholcus baka</i>	9,30	5	7,00	10	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus bakweri</i>	8,50	18	6,70	25	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus bamboutos</i>	10,50	9	8,10	13	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus batepa</i>	12,30	6	11,80	10	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus bicornutus</i>	10,96	5	9,60	8	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus bourgini</i>	16,60	9	14,00	6	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus calligaster</i>	8,40	15	8,10	28	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus ceylonicus</i>	11,90	32	10,40	24	Huber 2019
<i>Pholcus chang</i>	5,84	7	5,73	16	Yao & Li 2012
<i>Pholcus chappuisi</i>	9,80	32	8,60	45	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus chattoni</i>	14,40	13	11,60	11	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus chicheng</i>	11,16	18	8,19	10	Tong & Li 2010
<i>Pholcus circularis</i>	10,90	5	10,70	13	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus crassipalpis</i>	4,76	5	4,30	26	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus creticus</i>	5,70	5	5,90	10	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus crypticolens</i>	8,50	8	6,80	15	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus datan</i>	12,49	28	9,85	31	Tong & Li 2010
<i>Pholcus debilis</i>	9,40	27	7,40	34	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus decorus</i>	11,29	5	8,79	5	Yao & Li 2012
<i>Pholcus dixie</i>	13,10	7	10,50	7	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus doucki</i>	12,70	27	11,10	13	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus exilis</i>	10,29	26	9,85	13	Tong & Li 2010
<i>Pholcus fagei</i>	12,20	19	11,10	25	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus fragillimus</i>	6,50	6	7,30	8	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus fuerteventurensis</i>	8,90	8	7,60	6	Huber 2011

<i>Pholcus guineensis</i>	10,10	21	9,20	26	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus jinwum</i>	11,40	8	9,60	5	Huber 2001
<i>Pholcus kakum</i>	7,50	9	5,90	11	Huber 2009
<i>Pholcus kindia</i>	11,60	44	9,80	34	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus kribi</i>	4,00	5	3,20	15	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus kwamgumi</i>	7,60	14	5,50	21	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus lamperti</i>	16,30	16	13,20	22	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus leruthi</i>	10,10	39	8,80	37	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus manueli</i>	7,40	20	6,50	20	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus mulu</i>	14,90	5	13,30	13	Huber et al 2016c
<i>Pholcus olangapo</i>	10,40	10	9,20	11	Huber et al 2016c
<i>Pholcus opilionoides</i>	6,40	24	5,80	21	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus otomi</i>	10,90	5	10,50	6	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus pagbilao</i>	12,70	46	11,20	38	Huber et al 2016c
<i>Pholcus phalangioides</i>	10,60	24	10,60	21	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus phungiformes</i>	10,90	15	8,10	21	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus ponticus</i>	7,90	38	7,50	64	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus punu</i>	7,90	22	6,30	36	Huber et al 2014b
<i>Pholcus puranappui</i>	11,30	10	10,70	11	Huber 2019
<i>Pholcus shuangtu</i>	14,74	20	11,67	22	Yao & Li 2012
<i>Pholcus sogdianae</i>	7,80	5	7,20	11	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus soukous</i>	10,10	20	7,80	35	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus taarab</i>	8,02	5	6,20	5	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus taita</i>	15,10	22	12,00	41	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus tuyan</i>	11,28	5	8,97	6	Yao & Li 2012
<i>Pholcus twa</i>	9,70	21	8,70	52	Huber 2011
<i>Pholcus wangtian</i>	12,21	8	9,46	18	Tong & Ji 2010
<i>Physocyclus globosus</i>	10,79	26	6,49	31	Eberhard et al 1998
<i>Physocyclus guanacaste</i>	10,60	8	7,60	44	Huber 1998c
<i>Pisaboa estrecha</i>	4,28	5	3,20	10	Huber 2000
<i>Pisaboa marcuzzii</i>	3,70	13	2,80	11	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Pisaboa retracta</i>	3,60	8	2,80	7	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Pisaboa silvae</i>	3,70	14	2,60	22	Huber 2000
<i>Pribumia atrigularis</i>	9,50	5	7,20	8	Huber 2011
<i>Pribumia bohorok</i>	9,90	20	7,50	20	Huber 2011
<i>Pribumia minang</i>	8,86	5	6,70	12	Huber 2011
<i>Priscula acarite</i>	10,50	9	7,70	12	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Priscula andinensis</i>	10,10	25	7,60	28	Huber & Villarreal 2020

<i>Priscula lagunosa</i>	5,80	7	3,50	6	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Priscula paila</i>	8,10	7	5,00	11	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Priscula salmeronica</i>	8,20	5	4,70	11	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Priscula ulai</i>	9,80	13	4,90	6	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Priscula venezuelana</i>	14,90	16	11,90	15	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Psilochorus bromelicolus</i>	4,08	5	3,10	12	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Psilochorus californiae</i>	4,60	6	3,98	5	Slowik 2009
<i>Psilochorus imitatus</i>	5,70	5	4,54	5	Slowik 2009
<i>Psilochorus papago</i>	5,41	5	4,10	5	Slowik 2009
<i>Psilochorus pullulus</i>	4,34	5	3,81	5	Slowik 2009
<i>Psilochorus rockefelleri</i>	5,36	5	4,81	5	Slowik 2009
<i>Psilochorus utahensis</i>	6,11	5	5,50	5	Slowik 2009
<i>Quamtana bonamanzi</i>	1,89	28	1,51	22	Huber 2003c
<i>Quamtana embuleni</i>	2,21	7	1,73	17	Huber 2003c
<i>Quamtana entabeni</i>	5,75	10	4,54	15	Huber 2003c
<i>Quamtana merwei</i>	2,58	6	2,21	7	Huber 2003c
<i>Quamtana nyahururu</i>	3,30	15	2,40	5	Huber & Warui 2012
<i>Quamtana vidal</i>	2,12	6	1,63	10	Huber 2003c
<i>Saciperere catuaba</i>	5,20	21	4,00	62	Huber & Carvalho 2019
<i>Savarna kaeo</i>	5,60	16	4,80	24	Huber et al 2015b
<i>Savarna kraburiensis</i>	6,30	10	5,30	5	Huber et al 2015b
<i>Savarna tessellata</i>	6,00	12	5,40	5	Huber et al 2015b
<i>Savarna thaleban</i>	5,00	8	4,50	9	Huber et al 2015b
<i>Smeringopina africana</i>	15,24	5	11,50	10	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina ankasa</i>	9,60	8	7,50	28	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina attuleh</i>	8,70	5	7,40	7	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina belinga</i>	16,60	5	13,80	11	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina bineti</i>	11,30	19	9,70	39	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina bioko</i>	14,58	5	12,30	10	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina bomfobiri</i>	7,60	11	5,80	18	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina bwiti</i>	18,00	11	14,20	7	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina chaillu</i>	17,80	6	15,10	8	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina ebolowa</i>	16,40	15	12,90	22	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina etome</i>	16,90	12	13,20	21	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina fang</i>	8,30	23	5,20	44	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina guineensis</i>	14,10	11	10,70	24	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina mbouda</i>	12,30	20	9,30	26	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina moudouma</i>	9,90	12	7,50	26	Huber 2013

<i>Smeringopina nyasoso</i>	10,60	5	7,90	7	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina ogooue</i>	17,20	28	14,00	39	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina pulchra</i>	14,20	30	10,60	30	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina sahoue</i>	17,10	6	14,90	9	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina simplex</i>	16,20	16	12,40	18	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopina tchimbele</i>	17,70	5	15,30	9	Huber 2013
<i>Smeringopus atomarius</i>	10,50	9	10,00	11	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus bujongolo</i>	12,80	7	12,00	20	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus butare</i>	13,80	17	11,90	31	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus carli</i>	10,70	18	9,10	34	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus chogoria</i>	16,30	17	14,50	29	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus cylindrogaster</i>	10,50	6	7,90	20	Huber 2009
<i>Smeringopus dundo</i>	9,26	5	7,70	7	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus florisbad</i>	10,20	6	9,30	9	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus hanglip</i>	16,50	6	15,70	17	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus hypocrita</i>	9,50	5	9,60	5	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus kalomo</i>	12,90	24	11,00	46	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus koppies</i>	11,60	5	10,30	8	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus lesserti</i>	13,10	34	12,00	51	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus lineiventris</i>	13,20	6	12,40	8	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i>	8,90	10	7,30	33	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus lubondai</i>	13,70	5	10,70	12	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus luki</i>	9,90	10	8,20	22	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus mgahinga</i>	12,40	11	11,40	14	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus mpanga</i>	12,20	23	10,70	30	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i>	11,90	60	12,60	87	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus ngangao</i>	9,10	9	7,90	10	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus pallidus</i>	11,70	26	11,00	41	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus peregrinoides</i>	10,70	57	9,20	52	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus peregrinus</i>	10,60	37	10,10	42	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus roeweri</i>	12,20	41	9,80	80	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus sederberg</i>	10,40	5	9,70	9	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus similis</i>	10,70	8	10,10	22	Huber 2012
<i>Smeringopus turkana</i>	9,40	5	8,40	12	Huber 2012
<i>Spermophora abibae</i>	5,30	30	4,30	30	Huber et al 2014b
<i>Spermophora akwamu</i>	4,80	35	3,90	42	Huber & Kwapong 2013
<i>Spermophora awalai</i>	4,90	12	4,20	10	Huber et al 2014b
<i>Spermophora kyambura</i>	2,40	22	1,80	34	Huber & Warui 2012

<i>Spermophora maathaiae</i>	5,50	5	4,40	13	Huber & Warui 2012
<i>Spermophora peninsulae</i>	7,70	9	5,82	7	Huber 2003c
<i>Spermophora ranomafana</i>	4,46	46	3,45	44	Huber 2003a
<i>Spermophora sangarawe</i>	5,19	7	4,27	5	Huber 2003b
<i>Spermophora sumbawa</i>	1,46	15	1,20	20	Huber 2005b
<i>Spermophora usambara</i>	5,17	11	4,33	11	Huber 2003b
<i>Spermophora yao</i>	1,12	6	0,98	18	Huber 2001
<i>Stenosfemuraia quadrata</i>	5,30	8	3,50	7	Huber & Arias 2017
<i>Stenosfemuraia parva</i>	3,50	8	2,50	14	Huber & Arias 2017
<i>Stenosfemuraia pilosa</i>	3,10	14	2,30	19	Huber & Arias 2017
<i>Stygopholcus absoloni</i>	12,80	60	12,00	55	B.A. Huber unpubl. data
<i>Stygopholcus montenegrinus</i>	12,90	29	12,90	28	B.A. Huber unpubl. data
<i>Stygopholcus photophilus</i>	12,70	104	11,20	91	B.A. Huber unpubl. data
<i>Stygopholcus skotophilus</i>	12,80	35	12,40	36	B.A. Huber unpubl. data
<i>Systemita prasina</i>	7,30	56	5,40	50	Huber & Villarreal 2020
<i>Tainonia cienaga</i>	15,90	10	14,80	5	Huber & Astrin 2009
<i>Tainonia samana</i>	14,00	27	13,50	37	Huber & Astrin 2009
<i>Tainonia serripes</i>	16,10	30	15,30	61	Huber & Astrin 2009
<i>Teranga domingo</i>	8,20	15	6,60	19	Huber et al 2016b
<i>Tissahamia ethagala</i>	7,50	6	6,00	16	Huber 2011
<i>Tissahamia gombak</i>	7,80	13	6,10	17	Huber et al 2016b
<i>Tissahamia karuna</i>	8,20	9	6,80	13	Huber 2019
<i>Tissahamia kottawagamaensis</i>	9,60	8	7,80	13	Huber 2019
<i>Tissahamia ledang</i>	7,10	5	5,50	8	Huber et al 2016b
<i>Tissahamia maturata</i>	8,00	13	6,40	9	Huber 2019
<i>Tissahamia uludong</i>	7,10	9	5,50	9	Huber et al 2016b
<i>Trichocyclus arabana</i>	6,60	24	5,80	14	Huber 2001
<i>Trichocyclus nigropunctatus</i>	6,70	80	5,40	22	Huber 2001
<i>Trichocyclus nullarbor</i>	8,10	19	8,20	11	Huber 2001
<i>Tupigea ale</i>	4,80	11	3,30	6	Huber & Rheims 2011
<i>Tupigea angelim</i>	3,54	5	1,85	8	Huber & Rheims 2011
<i>Tupigea guapia</i>	4,90	7	3,50	9	Huber & Rheims 2011
<i>Tupigea lisei</i>	4,40	8	2,80	12	Huber 2000
<i>Tupigea teresopolis</i>	5,20	11	3,50	6	Huber & Rheims 2011
<i>Uthina huifengi</i>	6,00	7	5,40	13	Huber et al 2019
<i>Uthina huifengi</i>	7,85	6	6,95	27	Yao et al 2016
<i>Uthina hylobatea</i>	9,40	11	6,90	16	Huber et al 2019

<i>Uthina luzonica</i>	8,20	8	7,50	18	Huber 2001
<i>Uthina luzonica</i>	7,90	23	6,50	54	Huber 2011
<i>Wanniyala labugama</i>	2,80	5	2,20	6	Huber 2019
<i>Wanniyala ohiya</i>	5,40	5	4,50	15	Huber 2019
<i>Wanniyala orientalis</i>	3,50	17	3,10	38	Huber 2019
<i>Wanniyala upekkha</i>	3,50	5	3,10	9	Huber 2019
<i>Wanniyala viharekele</i>	3,30	11	2,70	12	Huber 2019
<i>Wugigarra bujundji</i>	10,50	9	8,70	13	Huber 2001
<i>Wugigarra kaurna</i>	11,30	15	9,10	8	Huber 2001
<i>Wugigarra mamu</i>	10,40	7	8,60	8	Huber 2001
<i>Wugigarra tjapukai</i>	11,40	7	9,70	11	Huber 2001
<i>Wugigarra undanbi</i>	4,30	8	2,80	8	Huber 2001

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